

A Study on the Factors Affecting the Purchase Intention of College Students towards Store-Bought Coffee

Noah Raphael D. Ramirez¹, Jehv Dane G. Serrano², Richard James Pua³,
Mr. Fulepro Alberto G. Madrilejos⁴

^{1,2,3}Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management, ⁴Adviser

DE LA SALLE UNIVERSITY – DASMARINAS

College of Tourism and Hospitality Management

Hospitality Management Department

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Abstract: The study aimed to determine the different factors affecting the purchase intention of coffee among college students at De La Salle University-Dasmariñas (DLSU-D). The respondents included were the one hundred five (105) first year and second year students during the School Year 2024-2025. The researchers used a descriptive and quantitative approach employing a survey. The principal instrument for data gathering was a validated self-made questionnaire with checklists. Findings revealed that the majority of respondents were female, aged 18-21 years old, in their second year, and received a weekly allowance of Php2,000 to Php3,000. The respondents identified several factors influencing their purchase intention for coffee. These include personal preferences for the characteristics of smell, taste, and bitterness. Additionally, the cleanliness of coffee shops affected their satisfaction and intention to purchase, highlighting the importance of environmental factors. From a psychological perspective, purchasing coffee helps them relax and unwind.

Keywords: Purchase Intension, Store-Bought, Coffee, Personal Factor, Environmental Factor, Psychological Factor.

1. INTRODUCTION

Coffee has become essential to many people's daily lives; it is now a part of their routine. Coffee is more than just a beverage; it helps people start their days, keep pace with their busy lives, and has numerous health benefits. People enjoy coffee for various reasons, including its taste and satisfaction, as well as the health benefits it can provide.

Coffee was discovered in the forests of Ethiopia's plateau in the 700s AD. However, in the 13th century, people began to roast coffee beans. The Spanish Franciscan Monks introduced coffee to the Philippines, specifically Lipa, Batangas, in 1740, where the first coffee tree was planted. The Philippines was ranked the world's 24th largest coffee producer in 2020. The Philippines is known for its high-quality coffee beans, and the country has recently earned international coffee awards and recognition.

In the specialty food sector, coffee shops are a prominent figure, offering different varieties of coffee. According to Euromonitor, it is expected that specialty coffee shops will continue to grow in the coming years due to good consumer demand. Filipinos are more into coffee drinking as it has become a popular social activity.

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Coffee shops are targeting a large market for students, it has become a status symbol, and it is a convenient place to study and for afternoon meetings. Coffee is widely regarded as an artisanal product rather than merely a beverage. As a result, coffee drinkers now prefer to patronize locally owned coffee shops that provide high-quality products and a distinct coffee experience.

Priorities and responsibilities differ among college students, which may influence their coffee consumption and purchase behavior towards coffee. Some students pursue part-time jobs while attending school, whereas other students are scholars. College students must, however, meet their prerequisites and maintain passing marks.

Due to the increasing demand for coffee, and the growing rate of coffee shops in the Philippines, Coffee shops are becoming more accessible to consumers. It is widely available, offered by fast food chains, restaurants, foreign coffee shops (i.e., Starbucks, Coffee Bean, Seattle's Best Coffee, and Tim Hortons), and the growing number of locally owned independent coffee shops. Aligned with this, the researchers aim to know the factors that influence consumers to purchase store-bought coffee based on their personal factors, environmental factors, psychological factors, and cultural factors.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The focus of the study is to determine the factors that influence consumers in purchasing store-bought coffee. This research specifically will seek answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondent in terms of:
 - a. Gender
 - b. Age
 - c. Year
 - d. Weekly Allowance
2. What level influences the consumers' purchasing intention on store-bought coffee based on the following factors:
 - a. Personal Factors
 - b. Environmental Factors
 - c. Psychological Factors
3. Is there a significant difference in the purchase intention of the respondents when grouped by profile?

Hypothesis of the Study

Pertaining to the questions of this study, the following hypotheses were put into test:

1. Based on the results of the study, there are no significant differences in the factors affecting the purchase intention of the respondents toward store-bought coffee when grouped according to age and year level. On the other hand, significant differences were found when the respondents were grouped according to gender and weekly allowance.

Significance of the Study

Specifically, the results of the study would be important and of great benefit to the following:

Administrators. The results of this study may provide the administrators of DLSU-D with specific data that may be used as a guide in helping students create a coffee shop environment that encourages learning, collaboration, and innovation, ultimately enhancing their needs and overall experience.

Students. The output of the study could encourage and guide students in promoting a culture of collaboration and innovation within the coffee shop environment. This can lead to increased engagement and an atmosphere for learning, motivating students to participate in activities like studying, completing assignments, and interacting with their professors, classmates, and friends.

Coffee shops owners/makers. The result of the investigation will provide coffee shop owners, planners, and makers with valuable insights and concepts for marketing strategies and enhancing their offerings. By understanding consumer preferences and purchasing intentions, they can improve product selection, design engaging promotional strategies, and create a more inviting atmosphere that meets the needs of their customers.

Readers: The results of the study will offer valuable insights into the significant role coffee plays in students' lives, highlighting its impact on their academic performance and social interactions. By understanding how coffee consumption influences study habits, motivation, and collaboration, readers can better appreciate the importance of coffee in fostering a conducive learning environment. This will also empower students to make informed choices about their coffee consumption, ultimately enhancing their overall academic experience and well-being.

Future Researchers. This study may serve as a guide to educational researchers in the field of tourism and hospitality to delve deeply through research on the urgent and relevant needs of the industry.

Definition of Terms

For clarity and better understanding of the study, the following terminologies were operationally defined:

Research Locale

This study will be conducted within Dasmariñas, Cavite, where the De La Salle University – Dasmariñas is located. Additionally, there is an increasing number of both commercial and locally owned coffee shops.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Purchase Intention

According to Shim et al. (2021), purchase intention refers to a consumer's willingness to acquire a certain product or service, and purchases are crucial to any business's ability to generate sales and capture market share. Purchase intention, particularly when customers are delighted with the items, stimulates more competitive companies to enter the market. Therefore, the corporate sector has identified purchasing intention as one of the most critical categories. Furthermore, buying behavior is critical for long-term business performance since it keeps customers' attention and enhances brand equity. Purchase intentions are important since consumers' expectations are hard to evaluate, and organizations usually discover them after the product is delivered.

Shim et al. (2021) investigated the determinants of purchasing intention at Starbucks Café in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. According to this study, despite the coffee industry's high economic output, it is highly competitive due to the lack of entry barriers and the ease with which customers may move to a different brand's café product.

Food Quality

Flavor is a key factor in restaurant choices since it enhances the sensory and emotional experience of dining. Since consumers care more about healthy lives, food quality has expanded to include nutrition and food safety, since wholesome food is related to customers' health and safety.

Menu diversity predicts meal quality (Rajput & Gahfoor, 2020). Flavorful food. Taste evaluation follows. Customers might predict flavor based on price, quality, labeling, and brand. Restaurant patrons value food quality. Presentation lightens up visitors (Carins, Rundle-Thiele & Ong, 2020). Freshness is defined by smell, juiciness, sharpness, and color (Rajput & Gahfoor, 2020).

Service Quality

In a service factory like a fast-food restaurant, making customers loyal by offering value-based service and food quality is a goal. Service quality is determined by the service procedure and customer perception. The service process emphasizes the store's physical, technical, human, and procedural features, impacting the consumer's service opinion. (Yang et al., 2021).

Most consumers assess restaurant service while eating, and perceived service quality is used to measure customer happiness. Self-service cafes and restaurants exist. Introverts will adore it since they don't need to socialize. Due to ease, user-friendliness, and fantastic online experiences, consumers favor optional online services (Liew et al., 2021)

Service providers provide high-quality services to be competitive. Restaurant service affects customer pleasure. Excellent service includes price, friendliness, neatness, care, variety, quickness, and menu consistency. Customer satisfaction depends on employee and customer communication. Service excellence boosts word-of-mouth, customer satisfaction, corporate image, customer recruitment, repeat business, and business performance (Rajput & Gahfoor, 2020)

Environmental

According to Rajput and Gahfoor (2020), clients desire good dining experiences, thus they look for a pleasant environment. The physical environment attracts new customers. PEQ increases financial performance and customer satisfaction. Consumers judge a restaurant's quality by its cleanliness, uniqueness, staff friendliness, physical condition, and environment-creating characteristics. Consumer satisfaction is influenced by the physical environment. Restaurants must be aesthetically attractive and distinctive.

Psychological

Emotions play a significant role in motivating or influencing consumer behavior. Consumers often make purchase decisions based on their emotional responses to products or brands. (Gaurav, 2023)

Social Motivation nowadays is also a powerful driver of consumer behavior. People are often motivated to conform to social norms and expectations, which can impact their purchasing decisions.

In summary, motivation is a complex and multifaceted driver of consumer behavior. It can be influenced by both internal and external factors, and understanding consumer motivation is crucial for businesses when developing marketing strategies and tailoring their offerings to meet consumer needs and desires.

Habit

D.I.D, (2020) concluded based on their survey in Ireland that 63% of the 500 respondents consumed two cups of coffee a day. Also, 35% and 25% of women and men respectively marked “extremely important” to drink coffee before starting their day.

According to (Clear, 2019) a habit is constructed through 4 stages viz 1) Cue – it is where customers notice the reward. 2) Craving- This is the stage where the customer wishes to acquire the reward. 3) Response- response is the action taken by the customer to acquire the reward. 4) Reward – finally, the customer is rewarded with two solutions a) Satisfaction and b) Learning. If the reward satisfies the customer, it is repeated, and a habit is developed. Whereas, if the customer’s desire isn’t satisfied, the customer won’t repeat it in the future. If critically seen, the prior three stages of the process are responsible for a behavior to occur, but the addition of 4th stage makes it a repetitive behavior. In other words, without the starting three stages, the behavior won’t establish and without the four stages, the behavior won’t be repeated.

Coffee in the Philippines

The year 1740, was when coffee was first introduced in the Philippines. The first coffee trees, which were a Mexican coffee variety, were planted in Lipa, Batangas by the Franciscan Monks. Lipa, Batangas became the coffee capital of the Philippines and started exporting coffee to America in the 1860s. By 1880, the Philippines became the only source of coffee beans worldwide due to coffee rust and became the fourth largest exporter of coffee beans. In contrast, coffee trees in Batangas were destroyed due to coffee rust. However, due to the favorable climate, and soil conditions, the Philippines lies within the equatorial zone called “The Bean Belt”. In addition to that, among the few nations that produce the four commercially viable coffee types - Liberica, Excelsa, Robusta, and Arabica are all varieties of coffee that are also produced in the Philippines (Philippine Coffee Board Inc, 2020).

Coffee Consumption of Filipinos

According to the Philippine Coffee Board Inc. (2020), the coffee production in the Philippines reduced and remains relatively low producing 62,000 metric tonnes of coffee in the year 2019, but also consuming 100,000 metric tonnes of coffee per annum. and as a result, the country is reliant on coffee production in the countries of Vietnam and Indonesia. 70% of the coffee shops in the Philippines import coffee beans.

According to Cigara (2021), the way people consumed coffee significantly changed. Due to the global coronavirus epidemic. In the year 2020, an average Filipino consumed 3.05 kg of coffee. The type of coffee drink most Filipinos prefer is soluble coffee. Though there is an increasing number of consumers of commercial and specialty coffee shops as it increases in popularity, this indicates that local coffee enthusiasts consume locally produced coffee.

The Philippines is the second-largest coffee consumer in Asia, with 80% of Filipinos drinking an average of 2.5 cups per day (MacDonnell, 2023).

Caffeine Intake of College Students

Coffee is commonly the most preferred source of caffeine as a central nervous system stimulant. Aside from coffee, tea, soda, chocolate, and energy drinks also contain caffeine, which other people prefer and commonly use as well. According to the study conducted by R., Bertasi et. al (2021), the number of caffeine intake is associated with the student’s year at school, which results in senior college students consuming more caffeine than lower-class students. The respondent’s main source of caffeine is coffee, which is 64% of the participants. As a result of the correlation of the motives for caffeine consumption between the greater caffeine intake of upper-class levels of education, students may believe that the

consumption of caffeine helps to improve students' academic performance. Additionally, there are two main reasons why college student's intake caffeine, one is for pleasure (43.9%) and the other is to study outside class (29.8%). In related studies, by Mahoney et. al and, Micoulaud-Franchi et. al (2019), both studies concluded that college students' main motivation for caffeine consumption is to increase wakefulness which will result in the enhancement of academic performance, followed by taste.

3. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The research paradigm aims to determine the behavior and factors that affect the purchase intention of college students in store-bought coffee.

The framework below shows strategies that the researchers followed to realize the objectives of their research.

Figure 1. The Paradigm of the Study

Figure 1. Conceptual Paradigm

Figure 1 demonstrates the paradigm of the study. The research paradigm gives a clear illustration of the variables involved in the study. The **input box** includes the profile of the respondents in terms of gender, age, year level, and weekly allowance. This also encompasses the assessment of first year and second year students regarding their purchasing intentions in terms of personal, environmental, and psychological factors.

In addition, the **process box** indicates the methods and procedures on how the research was conducted, the conduct of the survey with the use of questionnaires on the factors that affect the purchase intention of college students in store-bought coffee, followed by data gathering, analysis, interpretation and presentation of data.

The **output box** of the research paradigm highlights the study's contribution to the body of knowledge, specifically regarding marketing strategies for coffee shops to adapt to changing consumer behavior.

4. METHODOLOGY

This Chapter of the study presents the research design, research locale, data gathering procedures, and research instrument that is utilized by the researchers in collecting data and validating the study. The Paradigm of the study is analyzed and conceived, respectively.

Sampling Method

The research population of this study comprised of 107 first year and second year students of De La Salle University – Dasmariñas during the School Year 2024-2025. Only students who had completed first one semester and were enrolled for the second semester and beyond were included as participants in this study. Stratified random sampling was applied in this study.

In the presentation of the results, the respondents were given their respective codes to protect anonymity and in a way that does not embarrass the participants.

Research Gap

Based on the previous research, the deciding factors are personal, environmental, psychological, and cultural factors, which remain unexplored.

The advantage of the current research aims to fill the gap by providing a comprehensive analysis of the factors that influence college students' coffee consumption habits, which has been underexplored in existing literature. Furthermore, the present study specifically investigates these overlooked factors in the context of college students' purchase intentions towards store-bought coffee. The questionnaire was designed to gather insights into personal preferences, environmental influences, psychological motivations, and cultural attitudes, providing a deeper understanding of how these variables interact and collectively shape students' purchasing decisions.

Research Instrument

The principal instruments for data gathering were the questionnaire and checklists for recording data from documents. The questionnaire regarding the factors affecting the purchase intention of college students was adapted by the researchers from Ling (2023). The checklist for first year and second year students consisted of two main parts. The first part sought information about the personal details of the respondents, such as gender, age, year level, and weekly allowance. The second part focused on the respondents' perceptions on coffee products and coffee variations. It likewise included the expectations of the respondents that was indicated in Likert scale of 1-4, 4 as the highest and 1 as the lowest.

This was submitted for validation to a group of experts in the academe recommended by the administrators of the College of Tourism and Hospitality Management of DLSU-D. These experts made their comments and suggestions to improve the questionnaire based on the validity of the contents. This undergone reliability test using the test-retest technique. After which, the survey form was improved based on the results of the validation. The scores were processed after the retrieval of the data. The results of the validation became the bases in the preparation of the final survey form.

The respondents' response was consolidated and tallied to analyze the factors affecting their purchase intention regarding store bought coffee.

Data Gathering Procedures

In performing this research study, the researchers conducted an online survey via Google Forms. The researchers had leveraged social media as an online platform to gather the respondents needed for the study, college students at De La Salle University - Dasmariñas. The researchers created a survey questionnaire that targets the main objective of the study. Hence, the questionnaire covered the profile of the respondents, purchase behavior, and the factors that influence the purchase intention of college students toward coffee. To further improve the primary data collected and validate the study, an online search for relevant information conducted through a review of the literature acquired using textbooks, reports, and research articles.

Table 1. 4-Point Likert Scale

Weight	Scale Range	Verbal Explanation
4	3.50 – 4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.50 – 3.49	Agree
2	1.50 – 2.49	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree

Research Design

In conducting this study, the researchers used a descriptive and quantitative research approach in which the researchers investigated and gathered quantifiable data using purposive sampling. Moreover, the utilization of quantitative data enables the researchers to gain a thorough understanding of the Philippine coffee industry and the different factors influencing college students' purchase intention. The descriptive method was used to find facts and information regarding the subject matter. The purpose of this study was to determine the different factors affecting the purchase intention of college students on coffee.

Respondents of the Study

The population of the respondents was determined by the utilization of purposeful sampling for the descriptive and quantitative research design. Furthermore, the population shows the count of the demographic profile of college students within De La Salle University - Dasmariñas in terms of gender, age, year, and weekly allowance.

The survey questionnaire was conducted via Google Forms, which is the primary source of data. Furthermore, the findings were provided by the study's research objectives. The discussion was segmented into the following sections:

1. Profile of the Respondents
2. Factors in Purchase Intention of the Respondents
3. Is there a significant difference in the purchase intention of the respondents when grouped by profile?

Data Treatment and Analysis

To gain a clear understanding of the data, the researcher employed several statistical measures. **Frequency and Percentage Distribution** were used to determine the number and percentage of first year and second year students enrolled at DLSU-D during the 2024-2025 academic year, as well as to outline the demographic profile of the respondents. The **Mean** was calculated to identify the factors influencing the purchase intention of first year and second-year students toward store-bought coffee. **Standard Deviation** was also applied to assess the variability of these factors. To examine differences between groups, a **t-test for Independent Means** was used to determine common factors that affect purchase intention when students were grouped according to gender and year level. Finally, **One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)** was employed to assess significant differences in the factors affecting purchase intention, based on gender, age, year level, and weekly allowance.

5. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study is to determine the factors that influence the first and second year students at DLSU-D in purchasing store-bought coffee as basis for marketing strategies for coffee shops to adapt to the changing preferences of students. The researchers gathered information from 107 college students at DLSU-D who are coffee enthusiasts. Below is the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered to answer the specific problems raised in this study.

Problem 1: What is the profile of the respondent in terms of:

- 1.1. gender;
- 1.2. age;
- 1.3. year;
- 1.4. weekly allowance?

Table 2. Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Female	48	44.86
Male	59	55.14
Total	107	100

Table 2 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of gender. The table revealed that there are 48 or 48.86% female and 59 or 55.14% male respondents. Thus, majority of the respondents are male. According to Chen et al., (2022), gender factors have a significant impact on the indicators of fixation dwell time and fixation count on the area of interest. Male purchasing practices differ from those of female consumers. Male consumers' attention to positive comments is greater than that of female ones, they are more likely than female consumers to make purchase decisions easily. Additionally, the study of Gumilang et al., (2021) explained that most of the respondents were women, namely 58 %, while men were 42 %. There is a tendency that women prefer to buy coffee products at coffee-to-go shops compared to men, because in general women prefer to consume sweet coffee that is not too bitter. This suggests that women tend to prefer purchasing coffee products from coffee-to-go shops compared to men, as women generally favor sweeter coffee that is less bitter.

Table 3. Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Table 3
Profile of Respondents as to Age

Age	Frequency	Percent
18-21	68	63.55
22-25	34	31.78
26-29	5	4.67
Total	107	100

Table 3 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of age. The figure revealed that 68 or 63.55% fall within the bracket of 18-21 years old, 34 or 31.78% fall within the bracket of 22-25 years old, and 5 or 4.67% respondents fall within the bracket of 26-29 years old. Thus, majority of the respondents belonged to the 18-21 age category. This finding is supported by Nainggolan et al. (2022), who found that the average age of consumers frequently visiting coffee shops is 15-24 years or 82.5%. The majority of these consumers are students or individuals still in education. This suggests that coffee shops should tailor their marketing strategies and product offerings to appeal to a younger demographic, focusing on aspects such as affordability, convenience, and a conducive environment for studying and socializing.

However, the study by Varman and Sudarvel (2021) revealed that older consumers, specifically those in the age group up to 30 years, also tend to visit coffee shops and prioritize quality and health benefits in their coffee choices. These consumers include not only students but also married individuals. While younger consumers may be drawn to the trendy, social aspects of coffee culture, older consumers are more likely to seek out premium offerings and health-conscious options.

Table 4. Profile of the Respondents in terms of Year Level

Table 4
Profile of Respondents as to Year Level

Year	Frequency	Percent
1st year	50	46.73
2nd year	57	53.27
Total	107	100

Table 4 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of year level. The figure revealed that 50 or 46.73% are in their first year while 57 or 53.27% are in their second year level. This indicates that the majority of the students are in their second year level. This predominance of second year students suggests that they may have more experience and familiarity with the college environment, which could influence their purchasing behaviors and preferences regarding coffee.

Table 5. Profile of the Respondents in terms of Weekly Allowance

Table 5
Profile of Respondents as to Weekly Allowance

Weekly Allowance	Frequency	Percent
Php 1,000 - 2,000	34	31.78
Php 2,000 - 3,000	42	39.25
Php 3,000 - 4,000	19	17.76
Php 4,000 - above	12	11.21
Total	107	100

Table 5 shows that in terms of the weekly allowance for the respondents, 34 or 31.78% receive between Php 1,000 and Php 2,000, 42 or 39.25% receive between Php 2,000 and Php 3,000, 19 or 17.76% receive between Php 3,000 and Php

4,000, and 12 or 11.21% receive more than Php 4,000. Thus, majority of respondents receive a weekly allowance of between Php 2,000 and Php 3,000. This may be attributed to the financial capacity of the students, which can significantly impact their purchasing behaviors, particularly in terms of how they allocate their money for coffee. According to Goldstein (2021), the cost of specialty coffee drinks plays a major role in the total spending of consumers, influencing their purchasing decisions and frequency of visits to coffee shops.

Problem 2: What level influences the consumers’ purchasing intention on store-bought coffee based on the following factors:

1. Personal Factors
2. Environmental Factors
3. Psychological Factors

The succeeding tables present to this problem. The study revealed that the categories of the factors of the consumers’ purchasing intention on store-bought coffee are the following: (a) Personal Factors, (b) Environmental Factors, and (c) Psychological Factors.

Table 6. Distribution of the Respondents’ Assessment on the Factors that Influences Purchase Intension on Store-Bought Coffee and their Indicators in Category 1 Personal Factors

Table 6
Summary Distribution of the Factors that Influences the Consumers’ Purchasing Intention on Store-Bought Coffee and their Indicators in Category 1 Personal Factors as Viewed by the Respondents

CATEGORY	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Personal Factors				
1. Personal factors in purchasing coffee [Daily habit]	2.99	1.051	Agree	4
2. Personal factors in purchasing coffee [Increase energy levels]	3.33	0.855	Agree	2
3. Personal factors in purchasing coffee [Increase productivity and improve focus]	3.29	0.89	Agree	3
4. Personal factors in purchasing coffee [Coffee characteristics (smell, taste, and bitterness)]	3.49	0.92	Agree	1
Overall Mean	3.27	0.664	High	

Scale:

VERBAL INTERPRETATION OF THE MEAN		
	PER ITEM	OVER - ALL
1:00 - 1.49	Strong Agree	Very Low
1.50 - 2.49	Disagree	Low
2.50 - 3.49	Agree	High
3.50 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	Very High

Table 6 describes that among the 4 indicators in Category 1, **Personal Factors**, item 4, **personal factors in purchasing coffee [Coffee characteristics (smell, taste, and bitterness)]**, ranks 1 with a mean score of 3.49 and Standard Deviation of 0.92 which is verbally interpreted as Agree. The preceding findings show that the respondents place the highest importance on the sensory attributes of coffee when making purchasing decisions. Thus, majority of the respondents, factors such as the aroma, flavor, and bitterness of coffee are key determinants in their choice, indicating a strong preference for high-quality coffee characteristics. According to the study by Huang and Nuangjamnong (2022), purchase intention is influenced by customer satisfaction, along with factors such as service quality, perceived value, and store atmosphere. This suggests that other aspects, such as coffee characteristics, play a more prominent role in their purchasing decisions.

Item 1, **personal factors in purchasing coffee [Daily habit]**, ranks last with a mean score of 2.99 and Standard Deviation of 1.051 which verbally interpreted as Agree. These findings show that the respondents view their daily coffee habits as a less significant factor in their purchasing decisions compared to other personal factors.

An overall mean of 3.29 and Standard Deviation of 0.664 indicate that the respondents generally have a high level of influence from the indicators of Category 1, which are personal factors in purchasing coffee.

Table 7. Distribution of the Respondents' Assessment on the Factors that Influences Purchase Intension on Store-Bought Coffee and their Indicators in Category 2 Environmental Factors

Table 7
Summary Distribution of the Factors that Influences the Consumers' Purchasing Intention on Store-Bought Coffee and their Indicators in Category 2 Environmental Factors as Viewed by the Respondents

CATEGORY	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
2. Environmental Factors				
1. Environment factors in purchasing coffee [The environment of coffee shops gave me a relaxed feeling.]	3.52	0.635	Strongly Agree	2
2. Environment factors in purchasing coffee [The interior decoration and design of coffee shops encourage me to stay longer.]	3.37	0.795	Agree	3
3. Environment factors in purchasing coffee [The cleanliness of coffee shops fulfills my satisfaction level.]	3.55	0.587	Strongly Agree	1
4. Environment factors in purchasing coffee [The decoration and artifacts encourage me to recognize the coffee shops as high-class]	3.30	0.838	Agree	4
Overall Mean	3.44	0.57	High	

Scale: VERBAL INTERPRETATION OF THE MEAN

	PER ITEM	OVER - ALL
1.00 - 1.49	Strong Agree	Very Low
1.50 - 2.49	Disagree	Low
2.50 - 3.49	Agree	High
3.50 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	Very High

Table 7 shows that among the 4 indicators of Category 2, **Environmental Factors**, item 3, **environment factors in purchasing coffee [The cleanliness of coffee shops fulfills my satisfaction level.]**, ranks first among the indicators with a mean score of 3.55 and Standard Deviation of 0.587 which is verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree. These results suggest that the respondents place a high level of importance on the cleanliness of coffee shops when making their purchasing decisions. The strong agreement indicates that a clean environment significantly influences their satisfaction and overall choice of coffee shops, highlighting the priority they give to hygienic conditions in their coffee-buying experience. According to Sakdawekeesorn (2022), customers tend to spend more time in a store when the environment is stimulating. When consumers feel satisfied with the retail atmosphere, it significantly influences their mood and overall satisfaction.

Item 4, **environment factors in purchasing coffee [The decoration and artifacts encourage me to recognize the coffee shops as high-class]**, ranks last with a mean score of 3.30 and Standard Deviation of 0.838 which is verbally interpreted as Agree. These findings show that the respondents consider decoration and artifacts as elements that contribute to recognizing coffee shops as high-class. However, the majority view cleanliness as more significant in shaping their purchasing decisions.

An overall mean of 3.44 and Standard Deviation of 0.57 indicate that the respondents generally perceive environmental factors as having a high level of influence on their coffee purchasing decisions. This suggests that while environmental factors, such as the cleanliness and ambiance of coffee shops, are important, their influence is not overwhelmingly dominant compared to other factors.

Table 8. Distribution of the Respondents' Assessment on the Factors that Influences Purchase Intension on Store-Bought Coffee and their Indicators in Category 3 Psychological Factors

Table 8
Summary Distribution of the Factors that Influences the Consumers' Purchasing Intention on Store-Bought Coffee and their Indicators in Category 2 Psychological Factors as Viewed by the Respondents

CATEGORY	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
3. Psychological Factors				
1. Psychological factors [It makes me confident.]	3.09	0.996	Agree	4
2. Psychological factors [It helps me to relax my mind.]	3.46	0.677	Agree	1
3. Psychological factors [It helps to reduce stress.]	3.43	0.702	Agree	2
4. Psychological factors [It makes me productive.]	3.35	0.825	Agree	3
Overall Mean	3.33	0.625	High	

Scale: VERBAL INTERPRETATION OF THE MEAN

	PER ITEM	OVER - ALL
1.00 - 1.49	Strong Agree	Very Low
1.50 - 2.49	Disagree	Low
2.50 - 3.49	Agree	High
3.50 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	Very High

Table 8, **Psychological Factors**, exhibits the respondent’s views on the factors that influences their purchasing intention on store-bought coffee. It can be seen that under Category 3, there are four indicators. From the four indicators, number 2, **Psychological factors [It helps me to relax my mind]**, ranks 1 with a mean score of 3.46 and Standard Deviation of 0.677 which is verbally interpreted as Agree. These results imply that respondents generally agree that the psychological factor of relaxation significantly influences their intention to purchase store-bought coffee and means to help them relax. According to Chen (2022), factors such as usability, interactivity, sociability, professionalism, and opinion leaders can significantly enhance the emotional stimuli that drive purchase intentions. However, the lack of a positive influence from opinion leaders and usability on trust indicates that many consumers may be dissatisfied with the platform's features. Additionally, the varying effectiveness of opinion leaders may contribute to consumer uncertainty regarding the quality of coffee products. Moreover, favorable audience emotions have a positive association with purchasing intentions.

Item 1, **Psychological factors [It makes me confident.]**, ranks the last with a mean score of 3.09 and Standard Deviation of 0.996 which is verbally interpreted as Agree. These findings imply that the impact of coffee on confidence is perceived differently by individuals. Additionally, these findings suggest that marketing strategies should focus on highlighting the relaxation and flavor aspects of coffee.

An overall mean of 3.33 and a standard deviation of 0.625 indicate that the respondents generally experience a high level of influence from the indicators in Category 3, which includes psychological factors in purchasing coffee.

Problem 3: Is there a significant difference in the purchase intention of the respondents when grouped by profile?

Table 9. Comparison of the Respondents’ Assessment on the Factors that Influences Purchase Intension on Store-Bought Coffee when Grouped in Gender

Table 9

Comparison of the Respondents’ Views in the Purchase Intention and their indicators when Grouped in Gender

Gender	N	Mean	t	p	Interpretation
Female	48	3.268	-2.178	0.032	Significant
Male	59	3.504			

A cursory look at the aforementioned table shows that the computed t-value of 2.178 has a p-value less than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant differences is rejected. This indicated that male and female respondents have the same level of purchase intention. This suggests that gender plays a role in influencing the perceptions or behaviors related to the factor in question which should be considered in the decision-making process.

Table 10. Comparison of the Respondents’ Assessment on the Factors that Influences Purchase Intension on Store-Bought Coffee when Grouped in Age

Table 10

Comparison of the Respondents’ Views in the Purchase Intention and their indicators when Grouped in Age

Age	Mean	F	p-value	Interpretation
18-21	3.37	0.213	0.809	Not Significant
22-25	3.43			
26-29	3.51			

As shown in Table 10, results revealed that there is no significant difference in the purchase intention of the respondents when grouped by age, since the F-value of 0.213 has a p-value greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is not rejected. This indicated that the purchase intention of the respondents is the same across all age groups.

Table 11. Comparison of the Respondents' Assessment on the Factors that Influences Purchase Intension on Store-Bought Coffee when Grouped in Year level

Table 11

Comparison of the Respondents' Views in the Purchase Intention and their indicators when Grouped in Year Level

Year Level	Mean	t	p-value	Interpretation
1st year	3.397	-0.012	0.99	Not significant
2nd year	3.398			

A cursor looks at Table 11 reveals that there is no significant difference in the purchase intention of the respondents when grouped by year level, since the t-value of 0.012 has a p-value greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is not rejected. This indicated that the purchase intention of the first and second year respondents are the same.

Table 12. Comparison of the Respondents' Assessment on the Factors that Influences Purchase Intension on Store-Bought Coffee when Grouped in Weekly Allowance

Table 12

Comparison of the Respondents' Views in the Purchase Intention and their indicators when Grouped in Weekly Allowance

Weekly Allowance	Mean	F	p-value	Interpretation
Php 1,000 - 2,000	3.244	3.781	0.013	Significant
Php 2,000 - 3,000	3.327			
Php 3,000 - 4,000	3.722			
Php 4,000 - above	3.571			

As shown in Table 10, results reveal that there is a significant difference in the purchase intention of the respondents when grouped by weekly allowance, since the F-value of 3.781 has a p-value less than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected. This indicated that respondents with weekly income of Php3000-4000 have the highest level of purchase intention.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Considering the findings in this study, the following conclusions were drawn.

1. On the profile of respondents, the results indicate a predominance of male respondents compared to their female counterparts, prominently falling within the age bracket of 18-21 years old. Additionally, there is a higher representation of 2nd year students and majority receive a weekly allowance of Php2,000 to Php3,000.
2. The respondents agreed that the key **personal factors** influencing their purchase intention for store-bought coffee are the **smell, taste, and bitterness** of the coffee. Regarding **environmental factors**, the cleanliness and overall hygiene of coffee shops emerged as the most significant influence on their purchasing decisions. Additionally, under **psychological factors**, the role of coffee in helping them relax and unwind was identified as a major motivator for choosing store-bought coffee.
3. Based on the results of the study, the null hypotheses of no significant differences in the factors influencing consumers' purchasing intentions for store-bought coffee are accepted when grouped by age and year level, with a p-value less than 0.05. However, there are no significant differences for gender and weekly allowance, with a p-value greater than 0.05.
4. All three or 100% of the variables and their respective indicators of factors influencing consumers' purchasing intention for store-bought coffee perceived by the respondents as high which indicates that these factors are considered significant in shaping consumers' decisions to purchase coffee from stores.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby presented.

1. Since the majority of the respondents are male, store-bought coffee brands should explore and strengthen their promotion and marketing strategies through social media platforms. However, they should also make sure to target female consumers, so that their marketing appeals to both men and women.
2. The coffee shops should enhance their spaces to promote self-care and wellness by creating aesthetically pleasing and relaxing environments. Features like comfortable seating, soft lighting, and natural elements can foster a calming atmosphere, encouraging customers to view these spaces as sanctuaries for relaxation and well-being.
3. The coffee shops should maintain high cleanliness standards, regularly practice and inspect hygiene protocols, and prioritize enhancing the smell, taste, and bitterness of their products in order to improve customer satisfaction and encourage repeat customers.
4. Enhance brand visibility among students by sponsoring or partnering with campus events and activities.
5. Another study similar to the present study employing 1st year and 2nd year students not covered in the present study as respondents could be conducted to validate the results of this study.

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